

First record of the orb-web spider *Araneus holzapfelae* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT

The spotted orb-web spider *Araneus holzapfelae* Lessert, 1936 was described from Mozambique in 1936 and is only known from the type locality. This spider was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). Morphological features of the species were compared with illustrations and literature on the original description of *A. holzapfelae*. This is the first record of the occurrence of *A. holzapfelae* in South Africa, where it was recorded from five provinces. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: Biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Araneus*, represented by 642 species, is large genus with a wide distribution (World Spider Catalog 2020). *Araneus* species in South Africa are still poorly documented, and only 11 endemic species were listed in the first Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010). With the recent publication of Nentwig *et al.* (2020), five of these species are now listed as *nomen dubium*. The only recent paper on a South African *Araneus* included the transfer of *Larinia vara* Kauri, 1950 to *Araneus* (Marusik 2017).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of specimens were sampled that need to be identified (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). The identification of the araneids, of which most of the genera are not revised, are still a problem. One of the species sampled was identified as the spotted orb-web spider *Araneus holzapfelae* Lessert, 1936. The species is presently known only from the type locality in Mozambique. Morphological features of the species were compared with illustrations and literature on the original description of *A. holzapfelae*. It is presently still only known from the type locality. For the first time, images received for the SANSa Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012) were available to document the morphology of *A. holzapfelae* in South Africa, with notes on their general behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA).

TAXONOMIC TREATMENT

Araneus holzapfelae Lessert, 1936

Araneus holzapfeli Lessert, 1936: 246, fig. 40-42.

Description: Size: TL females 4–6 mm, males unknown. *Araneus holzapfeli* is a colourful species and both sexes are recognized by their abdomens decorated with red patterns and four black spots (Figs 1-5). Carapace yellow with eye region dark, with reddish-brown tint extending to the fovea over a slightly elevated area that bears scattered pale long setae (Figs 1, 3); carapace as wide as long, with eye region narrower; eye region with medial area bearing four eyes in two rows, with posterior row slightly procurved; lateral eyes positioned closed together, situated near the carapace edge (Fig. 5); anterior median eyes a little wider apart than the posterior median eyes. Legs similar in colour to carapace, yellow; legs sometimes tinted with green, slender; leg formula 1243; femora and tibiae bearing scattered dark long setae. Abdomen oval, slightly overhanging the carapace; dorsum with white background, decorated with reddish tinted longitudinal bands, merging anteriorly and posteriorly, shape varies between specimens; four black spots present on midline and near posterior end. Epigynum: as in Fig. 6

Behaviour: They are nocturnal orb-web spiders, making their webs at night and resting on vegetation during the day. They are easily sampled with sweep nets and were sampled from the Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011) and Grassland biomes. Specimens were also sampled from avocado orchards and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2013).

Figures 1–6. *Araneus holzapfelae*. (1) Female, dorsal view, from Ezemvelo Nature Reserve; (2) Same, lateral view; (3) Female, dorsal view, Empangeni; (4) Female from Richards Bay; (5) Immature female from Drummond; (6) Female epigyne. Photographs courtesy of Peter Webb (1-4) and Andrea Saunders (5).

Distribution: Mozambique. New records: South Africa (Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal and Mpumalanga) (Fig. 7).

Conservation status: The species is protected in the following conserved areas in South Africa: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa *et al.* 2010; Foord *et al.* 2019), Ezemvelo Nature Reserve, Faerie Glen Nature Reserve, Kruger National Park, Isandlwane Nature Reserve, Makelali Game Reserve (Whitmore *et al.* 2001) and uMkhuze Game Reserve. Due to its wide distribution range it is listed as Least Concern.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

SOUTH AFRICA. Gauteng: Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77), 1.iii.2014, R. Lyle, 1f, NCA 2014/2552; Pretoria, Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (-25.74, 28.19), 28.ix.2014, P. Webb, 1m, NCA 2015/3371. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88), 25.x.1977, P. Reavell, 1f, NCA 78/135; Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10) 18.vi.2013, P. Webb, 1f, NCA 2016/1640; iSimangaliso Wetland Park, uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), 14.iii. 2013, X. Combrinck, 1m, NCA 2104/3830; uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.62174, 32.24543), 20.ii. 2010, X. Combrinck, 1m, NCA 2011/2929; Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.359, 30.640), 15.iii.2011, M. Stiller, canopy fogging, 1f, NCA 2012/3363; Wakefield Farm, Nottingham Rd. (-29.4987, 29.9106), 24.xi.2015, P. Webb, 1m, NCA 2016/1983.

Limpopo: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04), 10.iii.2009, V. Gelebe, 1f, NCA 2009/916; Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04), 15.iii.2008, F. Mbedzi, 1f, NCA 2009/917; Little Leigh Farm, Louis Trichardt (-22.949, 29.870), 15.iii.2009, E. Stam, 1m, 1f, NCA 2009/1958, 2009/1957.

Mpumalanga: Brondal (20km NE of Nelspruit) (-25.35, 30.84), 2.xii.1997, M. van den Berg, 1f, NCA 98/249; Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Shabeni (-25.123, 32,237), 10.iii.2012, B. Reynolds, 1f, NCA 2013/2711.

Figure 7. Map showing distribution of *Araneus holzapfelae* in South Africa.

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